

Pre-print of: M. Taherzadeh, M. Baghani , M. Baniassadi, [Karen Abrinia](#) & M. Safdari (2016). Modeling and homogenization of shape memory polymer nanocomposites. Composites Part B: Engineering. DOI: [10.1016/j.compositesb.2015.12.044](#)

Modeling and Homogenization of Shape Memory Polymer Nanocomposites

M. Taherzadeh¹, M. Baghani^{1,*}, M. Baniassadi¹, K. Abrinia¹, M. Safdari²

¹School of Mechanical Engineering, College of Engineering, University of Tehran, Tehran, Iran

²Aerospace Engineering Department, University of Illinois, 104 S Wright St., Urbana, Illinois 61801, USA

Abstract

Increasing applications of shape memory polymer nanocomposites calls for reliable and effective modeling techniques. Finite element analysis (FEA) is one of the popular modeling techniques mostly used for this purpose. To perform FEA, an effective constitutive law is needed to extract the behavior of material in each integration point. In this study, we have employed 3D finite element modeling to study shape memory polymers (SMPs) loaded with perfectly dispersed Graphene Nanoplatelets (GNPs). In the current work, a novel scheme is used to create representative volume elements for the purpose of modeling, and a 3D constitutive equation is derived to describe the characteristic thermomechanical behavior of SMPs. Several realizations of SMP nanocomposites with different volume fractions and aspect ratios of GNP inclusions are generated and modeled, and effective mechanical properties of generated microstructures are estimated using volume-averaged values. It is observed that SMPs loaded with 3% by volume GNP inclusions recover their permanent shape when they are subjected to a small strain thermomechanical cycle. Furthermore, a considerable improvement on the elastic modulus of the composites is observed upon increasing volume fraction or aspect ratio of GNP inclusions.

Keywords

A. Polymer-matrix composites (PMCs), A. Smart materials, A. Nano-structures, C. Finite element analysis (FEA)

1 Introduction

Shape memory materials are a class of smart materials that recover their original (permanent) shape from a deformed state (temporary shape) which is known as shape memory recovery. In most cases, external stimulus such as heat, magnetism, or electricity is applied to stimulate shape memory recovery [1-3]. Since first discovery of shape memory effect in polymers, many research efforts in this field have been carried [4, 5]. Compared to other types of smart materials such as shape memory alloys, shape memory polymers (SMPs) have low density, low cost, low energy consumption, excellent manufacturing capability and the ability to withstand large elastic deformation [6-8]. Shape memory polymers are utilized in wide range of applications such as medical, micro-electromechanical systems and advanced technologies in the aerospace [9, 10].

*Correspondence to: M. Baghani (baghani@ut.ac.ir).

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Despite all impressive characteristics of SMPs, the most noticeable drawback for SMPs is their poor elastic properties [11] which impedes the applications of SMPs when large recovery stress is required, e.g. in actuators. In order to overcome such limitations, a variety of reinforcements are used in SMP composites [12, 13]. Needless to say, recent developments in the fabrication of nanoscale materials such as Graphene [14], graphite, carbon nanotubes [15, 16], and clay also increased academic and industrial interests on using these nanomaterials as reinforcement in other materials including SMPs.

Due to difficulties in experimental characterizations, other methods such as analytical and numerical simulations may be employed as an alternative to experimental methods [17, 18]. Mori-Tanaka (MT) [19], and the Halpin-Tsai [20] are two of the most popular analytical mechanic-based composite stiffness models that are widely used for modeling composite structures [21]. These methods are not able to precisely account for the interaction between adjacent particles. Additionally, the micro-stress that is involved with each individual inclusion cannot be evaluated by these methods [22]. In last decades, numerical methods, e.g., finite element method (FEM), has attracted a great deal of interest to be utilized in simulation as well as design of composite structures [23, 24]. Statistical continuum mechanics techniques also offer useful tools for characterization and reconstruction of heterogeneous materials based on statistical correlation function [23, 25].

In this study, 3D representative volume elements (RVEs) are generated to simulate the stress-strain-temperature relationship of randomly distributed Graphene nanoplatelets-reinforced shape memory polymer composite. In order to evaluate thermo-mechanical response of the composite, the model has been assumed as a mixture of elastic Graphene Nanoplateletes (GNPs) inclusions and SMP matrix. SMP matrix itself is divided into two phases, rubbery and glassy, and the fraction of each phase is directly related to the temperature [26]. To capture the thermomechanical response of SMP, a thermodynamically-consistent constitutive model has been developed [3, 26]. The stiffness tensor of the elastic GNP is identified by ultrasonic and static tests [27]. In all cases, 7% axial strain is applied and the effects of aspect ratio of the inclusions and volume fraction on the effective elastic properties are presented. Two different thermomechanical cycles are applied on the model, stress-free strain recovery cycle and fixed-strain stress recovery cycle. In the stress-free strain recovery cycle, the model returns from deformed state (temporary shape) to their original (permanent) shape due to rising the temperature. However, in the second cycle, the model is prevented to return to its original shape during the heating the materials. This study also investigates the important effect of imperfect GNP/SMP interfaces on shape memory polymer nanocomposites. Cohesive surface energy between GNP nanoparticles and a polymer reported elsewhere [28] is introduced into finite element models to capture GNP/polymer debonding and its subsequent effect on the mechanical properties of the nanocomposite system under investigation. Finally, key observations of the study are summarized followed by a series of concluding remarks.

2 Constitutive Equations for SMP

In this section, the shape memory effect in a stress-strain-temperature diagram is described. As it is shown in Fig. 1, point \boxed{a} is the start state in this diagram where SMP holds its permanent shape. At this state a specified strain is applied on the SMP and it demonstrates a rubbery behavior up to point \boxed{b} . Then the strain is fixed and the temperature is decreased until the rubbery phase is converted into Glassy phase T_l (temporary shape at point \boxed{c}). Then the material is unloaded. Because of the high stiffness of the glassy phase polymer, the strain slightly recovers (point \boxed{d}). Finally the temperature rises and SMP recovers its permanent shape at point \boxed{a} . This cycle is called stress-free strain recovery in SMP applications. On the

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other hand, SMP could have gone from point \boxed{d} to point \boxed{e} , if the strain at point \boxed{d} was kept fixed and the temperature was increased. In this way, the cycle is called fixed-strain stress recovery (shown in Fig. 1 with dotted line).

Fig. 1. Stress-strain-temperature diagram showing the thermomechanical behavior of SMP under strain or stress recovery processes.

Now, a brief explanation of the small strain constitutive model proposed by Baghani et al [3] is provided. In this model an equivalent RVE of SMP consisting of a frozen and an active phase has been used. According to the mixture rule, the total strain is given in the following relation:

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = \varphi_a \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^a + \varphi_f \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^F + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^T, \quad (1)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^a$ and $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^F$ denote elastic strain in the active and frozen phase, respectively and $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^T$ denotes the thermal strain which is evaluated by $\alpha^T dT$ and α^T is the effective thermal expansion coefficient. In this relation, φ_a and φ_f denote the volume fraction of the active and frozen phase, respectively. Both φ_a and φ_f are function of temperature. The strain in the frozen phase $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^F$ is decomposed into two parts such that

$$\varphi_f \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^F = \varphi_f \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^f + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{is}, \quad (2)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^f$ is the elastic strain in the frozen phase and $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{is}$ is the inelastic stored strain. As a result, the total strain is the weighted summation of the strains in each phase.

Assuming temperature decreasing, the strain in the newly generated glassy phase, already been in the rubbery phase, had experienced the $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^a$ previously. Then $\varphi_f \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^F$ is defined as:

$$\varphi_f \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^F = \varphi_f (\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^f + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{-f}) = \varphi_f \left(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^f + \frac{1}{V_f} \int_{V_f} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^a dv \right) = \varphi_f \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^f + \frac{1}{V} \int_{V_f} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^a dv, \quad (3)$$

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where V_f and V are volume of the frozen phase and the total volume of the RVE, respectively. In equation (3), strain in the frozen phase is divided into two parts: strain in the old frozen phase, $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^f$, and strain in the newly generated frozen phase, $\bar{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^f$. The term “ $\varphi_f \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^f$ ” is called as the stored strain and it is denoted by $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{is}$. We recast equation (3) to

$$\varphi_f \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^F = \varphi_f \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^f + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{is}. \quad (4)$$

In the cooling process, $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{is}$ is defined by

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{is} = \int \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^a d\varphi_f. \quad (5)$$

In the heating process, the strain stored in the frozen phase should be relaxed. This is mathematically expressed by

$$\varphi_f \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^F = \varphi_f (\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^f + \bar{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^f) = \varphi_f (\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^f + \frac{1}{V_f} \int \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{is} dv) = \varphi_f \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^f + \frac{1}{V} \int \frac{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{is}}{\varphi_f} dv, \quad (6)$$

which in a more compact form is

$$\varphi_f \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^F = \varphi_f \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^f + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{is}. \quad (7)$$

Thus, the total strain could be recast to

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = \varphi_a \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^a + \varphi_f \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^F + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^T + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{is}. \quad (8)$$

In addition, the stored strain obeys the following evolution law

$$\dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^{is} = \dot{\varphi}_f \left[k_1 \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^a + k_2 \frac{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{is}}{\varphi_f} \right]; \begin{cases} k_1 = 1, k_2 = 0, \dot{T} < 0 \\ k_1 = 0, k_2 = 1, \dot{T} > 0, \\ k_1 = 0, k_2 = 0, \dot{T} = 0 \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

Now, based on a first order rule of mixture, the convex free-energy density function Ψ is defined by

$$\Psi(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}, T, \varphi_f, \varphi_a, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^a, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^f, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{is}) = \varphi_a \Psi^a(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^a) + \varphi_f \Psi^f(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^f) + \Psi^\lambda(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}, T, \varphi_f, \varphi_a, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^a, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^f, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{is}) + \Psi^T(T), \quad (10)$$

where Ψ^a and Ψ^f stand for the Helmholtz free-energy density function of the active and frozen phases, respectively. Also Ψ^T denotes the thermal energy and the term Ψ^λ enforces kinematic constraint in the following form

$$\Psi^\lambda(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}, T, \varphi_a, \varphi_f, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^a, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^f, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{is}) = \boldsymbol{\lambda} : [\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} - (\varphi_a \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^a + \varphi_f \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^f + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{is}) - \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^T], \quad (11)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\lambda}$ is the Lagrange multiplier. Applying the second law of thermodynamics in the sense of the Clausius-Duhem inequality, the following equation is obtained

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$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \boldsymbol{\lambda} = \frac{\partial \Psi^a}{\partial \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^a} = \frac{\partial \Psi^f}{\partial \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^f}. \quad (12)$$

Equations (12) is consequence of the basic assumption of simultaneous existence of the rubbery and glassy phases.

3 Three-dimensional Modeling and Numerical Considerations

Finite element method is one of the most powerful numerical schemes that is used for the modeling and simulation of a wide range of engineering problems. Because of high computational costs and modeling complexities, a perfect realistic modeling of a nanocomposite is extremely challenging or might be impossible. One way to bypass some of these limitations in the simulation of composite materials is to exchange the macroscopic model with a large enough representative volume element.

In this section, Finite Element Method has been utilized for the evaluation of effective elastic properties of two-phase SMP composites filled with randomly distributed and oriented GNPs. The geometry of inclusions plays an important role on the overall effective mechanical properties [29, 30]. Thus, in this work we also study the effect of inclusion geometry in our finite element model where we change the aspect ratio of inclusions with platelet geometry. For a platelet, by aspect ratio we denote the ratio between the diameter and thickness. In the modeling procedure, particles are subject to hard-core constraint where we avoid intersection or contact between them. The commercial finite element code ABAQUS (V6.10) is used to carry out the simulations.

In order to reconstruct the RVE similar to experimentally fabricated random composites, 3D inclusions are randomly distributed and oriented in the RVE. In Fig. 2, samples of 3D cubic RVE with different aspect ratio of inclusions have been shown. To automate the model generation process, RVEs are constructed in ABAQUS using an in-house Python script. Also, the position of the center of particles and their orientation, are first computed using an in-house C++ code [31]. The modeling parameters are adjusted in the C++ code.

To simulate SMP matrix in the finite element model, the 3D constitutive equations described in section 2 [3], are implemented in the finite element software ABAQUS/Standard, through a user-defined material subroutine (UMAT). The material parameters used in all simulations are listed in Table 1. The details of material model used here are given elsewhere [3, 26] where the model has been verified with several experimental data sets. It is noted that the elastic properties of GNPs are listed in Table 2 [27].

Table 1 Material parameters of SMP modeling [3].

Material parameters	Values	unite
E^a, E^f	15.2, 2600	MPa
ν^a, ν^f	0.49, 0.4	–
T_l, T_g, T_h	25, 46, 62	$^{\circ}C$
ρ	1100	kg / m^3
φ_f	$\frac{\tanh(\frac{T_h - T_g}{b}) - \tanh(\frac{T - T_g}{b})}{\tanh(\frac{T_h - T_g}{b}) - \tanh(\frac{T_l - T_g}{b})}, b = 4.817^{\circ}C$	–

Table 2 The elastic constants of Graphene Nano-Platelet reported by Blakslee [27].

	C_{11}	C_{12}	C_{13}	C_{33}	C_{44}	C_{66}
GNP elastic constants (GPa)	1060	180	15	36.5	4	440

To account for the effect of size dependency and determine the proper size for RVEs, several simulations are carried out initially. In these preliminary simulations different RVE sizes with the same inclusion volume fraction were created (see Fig.2) to measure the size dependency of calculated results and determine an acceptable RVE size.

The intension of this research is to study the effect of the aspect ratio and the volume fraction on the mechanical behavior of SMP nanocomposite. Making a realistic model for nanocomposite is beyond the scope of the current work. In all numerical studies on composite reinforced with platelet shaped inclusions such as Graphene, GNP, clay nanoplatelet [32-35], inclusions have been modeled as thin circular disks and in a few cases as rectangular thin disks. This simplistic model could provide useful information about the above mentioned parameters on the overall stress-strain behavior of the composite materials.

In this study, the interface between nanoparticles and the matrix are assumed to be perfect. In practices, interface between nanoparticles and GNPs may undergo failure and debonding. To investigate the potential effect of interface debonding on the mechanical properties of the nanocomposite, we introduce imperfect interfaces with associated surface energy into our finite element model for one of the cases. For this purpose, we use cohesive zones to the interfaces between GNPs and matrix and assume a bilinear traction-separation law [36]. The cohesive model used here is parameterized by an initial stiffness, a peak traction value, and a critical surface energy for failure. For GNPs/SMP system, these cohesive zone parameters can be extracted from molecular dynamics studies or by experimental measurements which is beyond the scope of the current study. An alternative choice is to find a material which has a similar structure to SMPs with known cohesive zone parameters. Using molecular dynamics, Awasthi et al. [28] have studied the interfacial interactions between Graphene and polyethylene. Molecular structure of

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Table 3. Cohesive zone model parameters for interfacial interaction between GNP and polyethylene [28].

Fracture mode	Fracture energy (mJ/m^2)	Peak traction (MPa)
Shear mode	331.650	108.276
Normal mode	246.525	170.616

The RVEs are meshed using 4-node linear tetrahedral elements (C3D4 elements). To evaluate the elastic modulus, a small uniform strain (7%) is applied on one side of the RVE cube where the opposite side is kept fixed in its normal direction and the other side is allowed to move freely. The corresponding stresses are calculated using reaction forces on each side. The effective elastic modulus and Poisson’s ratio are estimated employing the Hooke’s law for isotropic materials. To ensure that the selected RVE obeys Hooke’s law for isotropic materials, the homogenized stiffness tensor of the RVE is extracted. A RVE loaded with 0.5% of GNPs with aspect ratio 10 is subjected to six different load cases and each time only one normal or pure shear strain is applied to the faces. The effective stiffness tensor for the described RVE extracted by volumetric homogenization of the resultant stresses is examined as measure of isotropy.

Fig.2. Different sizes of RVEs that were used in the size dependency checking simulations. The volume fraction for all of the above models was 0.005. There were 10, 20, 40, 80, 240, 320, 400, and 600 inclusions in the models (a), (b), (c), (d), (e), (f), (g), and (h), respectively.

4 Numerical Results

To check the convergence of the finite element results, the dependency of the reported results to the RVE size are considered (Fig 3). The size of RVE is closely related to the dimension and geometry of inclusions [31]. The size of RVE must be large enough eliminate the effect of boundary distribution of inclusions

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[37, 38]. Fig.3 shows, the finite element results for elastic modulus of the SMP composite at T_h for different RVE sizes including GNP inclusions with the aspect ratio of 20. The volume fraction of particles is 0.5% for all cases. As an overall trend, an increase in the number of inclusions enhances the accuracy of the FE results. Nevertheless, utilizing larger RVE sizes is limited by the difficulties in mesh generation step and it is also associated to higher computational costs. Thus, a maximum acceptable relative error was adopted in the simulation to determine the acceptable size of the RVE. As shown in Fig. 3, increasing the size of RVE or equally increasing the number of inclusions, the estimated composite to matrix material elastic modulus ratio (E_c / E_m) converges to a constant value. Assuming this constant value as the accurate result, the relative error is calculated. In addition, we assume the relative error to be less than 4%, and the results from a series of simulations show that the minimum size for RVEs with the volume fraction of 0.5% should be above of the demonstrated line depicted in Fig. 4. According to these results, an RVE with volume fraction of 0.5% and including 50-nm diameter inclusions is an acceptable RVE.

Fig.3. Effect of the RVE size on the SMP nanocomposite effective elastic modulus (E_c / E_m) for different GNP inclusions. The volume fraction of inclusions is 0.5%.

Using cohesive zone model with parameters listed in Table 3, the behavior of a SMP/GNP nanocomposite system is computationally investigated under a simple tension test. The average stress/strain diagram obtained is shown in Fig.4. Based on this diagram, a linear response for stress-strain behavior is observed for strains less than 4%. At low strain levels, SMP/GNP interfaces show negligible failure, mostly limited to the stress concentration sites, therefore the assumption of perfect bonding for the interfaces is valid. For strain levels larger than 4%, the stress-strain response starts to deviate from linearity, however the extent of nonlinearities remain small for up to 6% strains. It is worth noting that for all modeling efforts reported here, the tensile strains never exceeds 7%, therefore the assumption of perfect interface should provide tight estimates for the properties reported. However, for strains larger than 7%, initial damage sites start to propagate along the interfaces and the total strain energy stored in the system will be reduced by the formation of free (debonded) GNP/SMP surfaces in the system as shown in Fig. 5. As a result, the total elastic stiffness of the GNP/SMP nanocomposite system diminishes.

Fig.4. Homogenized stress/strain response for a RVE of the GNP/SMP nanocomposite system loaded with 0.5% GNPs under simple tension test (the temperature is set to T_h and remains constant).

Fig.5. Partial debonding of interfaces in the GNPs/SMP nanocomposite system. Plot shows distribution of effective stress (in von Mises) over a cross-section of the RVE undergoing strain levels above 7%.

Based on the initial observation presented, for the rest of the study, a perfect bonding for interfaces is assumed and a proper RVE size is utilized. As it is mentioned in section 2, a specified strain was applied to the rubbery SMP sample. Then, the temperature was decreased to transform SMP to the glassy phase. In the next step, the constraints were removed and the sample was unloaded. During this process, SMP released a negligible elastic strain. Finally, the temperature was increased and SMP recovered its

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$$T^* = \frac{T - T_l}{T_h - T_l}, \quad (13)$$

where T_l and T_h are identified in Table 1. The diagrams illustrate that the permanent shape was completely recovered after a stress-free strain cycle. The reported results are reasonable because the applied strain is in the range of small strains and the elastic behavior of GNPs and SMP are therefore considered. Furthermore, the results prove that by increasing the volume fraction of inclusions, the effective elastic modulus of the composite increases. Also, this result is obtained in fixed-strain stress recovery cycle.

Fig. 6. Temperature-Strain-Stress diagram of free-stress strain recovery cycles for three different SMP nanocomposite (volume fractions of 1%, 2%, and 3%) and pure SMP.

To simulate the SMP nanocomposite in fixed-strain stress recovery cycle, three configurations were considered for which RVEs with different volume fraction of inclusions were presented. For the first configuration, five composites with inclusion's aspect ratio of 10 and volume fractions of 0.05%, 1%, 1.5%, 2%, and 2.5% were considered. For the second configuration, the aspect ratio of inclusions was 20 and there were six different composites models (volume fractions of 0.5%, 1%, 1.5%, 2%, 2.5% and 3%). For the third configuration, four different composites with inclusion's aspect ratio of 40, and volume fractions of 0.5%, 1%, 1.5% and 2% were considered. For each of the above composites, a fixed-strain stress recovery cycle was applied to RVE. In this cycle the temperature in the deformed RVE was decreased and the generated glassy phase stored the strain. Then the RVE was unloaded to release the stored elastic strain. In the final step, the strain was remained constant and then the temperature was

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The results of finite element simulation for the first, second and third configurations are presented in Fig.7, Fig.8, and Fig.9, respectively. As shown in these figures, the recovery stress increases due to an increase in the volume fraction of GNP inclusions. Moreover, by comparing the reported results for different values of inclusions aspect ratio, it can be concluded that both the recovery stress and the elastic modulus increase as the aspect ratio of the particles increases for the same volume fraction.

Fig. 7. Temperature-strain-stress diagram of fixed-strain stress recovery cycles for three different SMP nanocomposites (aspect ratio of 10 and volume fractions of 0.5%, 1.5%, and 2.5%) and pure SMP.

Fig. 8. Temperature-strain-stress diagram of fixed-strain stress recovery cycles for three different SMP nanocomposites (aspect ratio of 20 and volume fractions of 0.5%, 1.5%, and 2.5%) and pure SMP.

Fig.9. Temperature-strain-stress diagram of fixed-strain stress recovery cycles for three different SMP nanocomposites (aspect ratio of 40 and volume fractions of 0.5%, and 1.5%) and pure SMP.

As mentioned in the previous section, a series of simulations were carried to ensure that the reconstructed RVE for the nanocomposite obeys the Hooke's law for isotropic materials. Equation (14) shows the estimated stiffness tensor for a sample RVE. Comparing the estimated stiffness tensor with the stiffness

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 tensor of an isotropic material, it is clear that for the selected RVE size, the assumption of isotropic material property for the RVE/SMP nanocomposite system studied here is valid.

$$\mathbf{C} = \begin{bmatrix} 2.7212 & 2.6163 & 2.6128 & 0.0040 & 0.0012 & 0.0004 \\ 2.6156 & 2.7225 & 2.6153 & 0.0021 & 0.0023 & 0.0020 \\ 2.6141 & 2.6166 & 2.7247 & 0.0002 & 0.0004 & 0.0024 \\ 0.0002 & 0.0001 & 0.0011 & 0.1068 & 0.0001 & 0.0007 \\ 0.0002 & 0.0002 & 0.0002 & 0.0001 & 0.1067 & 0.0001 \\ 0.0001 & 0.0002 & 0.0000 & 0.0007 & 0.0002 & 0.1068 \end{bmatrix} * 10^8 \text{ Pa} \quad (14)$$

Fig.10 summarizes all of the modeling results obtained. This figure illustrates the effect of the volume fraction and aspect ratio of inclusions on the elastic modulus of SMP nanocomposite. From this figure, it is clear that an increase in either values of the aspect ratio or the volume fraction enhances the elastic properties of SMP nanocomposites. For instance, by increasing the volume fraction of a GNP, with an aspect ratio of 20, up to 3% the elastic modulus of the composite rises by twofold. The results of all modeling are listed in Table 4. In this Table, ratios of the elastic modulus and the effective recovery stress of the composite, to those for the pure SMP are reported for a variety of SMP composites.

Fig. 10. Effects of aspect ratio and volume fraction of inclusions on the elastic modulus.

Table 4 Elastic property and recovery stress of SMP nanocomposite obtained by finite element simulations.

Aspect ratio of inclusions	Volume fraction (%)	$(E_c / E_{SMP})^*$	$(RS_c / RS_{SMP})^{**}$
10	0.5	1.0498±0.0020	1.0838±0.0034
	1	1.1169±0.0047	1.1528±0.0061
	1.5	1.2199±0.0088	1.2586±0.0103
	2	1.3171±0.0127	1.3584±0.0143
	2.5	1.4048±0.0162	1.4485±0.0179
20	0.5	1.0827±0.0033	1.1176±0.0047
	1	1.2119±0.0085	1.2504±0.0100
	1.5	1.4020±0.0161	1.4455±0.0178
	2	1.5820±0.0233	1.6301±0.0252
	2.5	1.8009±0.0720	1.8541±0.0342
	3	1.9787±0.0391	2.0359±0.0414
40	0.5	1.1933±0.0077	1.2312±0.0092
	1	1.4865±0.0195	1.5321±0.0213
	1.5	1.8939±0.0358	1.9488±0.0380
	2	2.2433±0.0497	2.3059±0.0522

* Ratio of elastic modulus of the composite to that of the pure SMP

** Ratio of recovery stress of the composite to that of the pure SMP

5 Summary and Conclusions

In this study, a finite element modeling for the characterization of the elastic properties of SMP nanocomposites was presented to take into account the effects of volume fraction and aspect ratio of nano-fillers on the composite material. A user-defined material subroutine (UMAT) was used to implement 3D constitutive behavior of SMP into non-linear finite element software ABAQUS/Standard. Linear elastic Orthotropic and isotropic stiffness were considered for Graphene nanoplatelets inclusions and SMP matrix, respectively. To account for the limited size effects and possible boundary condition effects, a series of finite element simulations were carried out to determine suitable RVE size.

The effect of imperfect GNP/SMP interface was also investigated, and it is concluded that for strain levels utilized in the current study the assumption of perfect bonding between GNP nanoparticles and SMP polymer matrix is acceptable. In the next step, as series of RVEs with varying inclusion volume fraction were created to apply free-stress strain recovery cycle and observe the shape recovery behavior. Finally, three classes of GNPs with different aspect ratio for inclusions (10, 20, and 40) were considered. For each aspect ratio, several RVEs with different volume fractions (from 0.5% up to 3%) were modeled. The results indicated that elastic properties and recovery stress increase with an increase in either volume fraction or aspect ratio of inclusions. The recovery stress increases by about 100% when using 1.7% or 3% GNP with aspect ratio of 40 or 20, respectively.

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